

EVALUATION OF ZOOPLANKTON DIVERSITY IN ECHARA RIVER, NIGERIA

¹Ude, E. F., ¹Ugwu, L. L. C. and ²Mgbenka, B. O.

1. Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Ebonyi State University, P. M. B. 053, Abakaliki. 2. Department of Zoology, Fisheries and Aquaculture Unit, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Preliminary assessment of the zooplankton in Echara River was conducted from September 2006 to February 2008 to identify the major groups. Four groups (protozoans, rotifers, cladocerans and copepods) and 21 species were recorded. Cladocerans had the highest number of species (8), while rotifers and copepods each had 5 species. The least in terms of species diversity was protozoan. Each group differed significantly ($P < 0.01$) from the other. There was non-significant interaction between rotifers, cladocerans and copepods. However, protozoan and nauplii showed significant ($P < 0.05$) interactions. There was also significant difference ($P < 0.01$) between the mean values of the groups in different locations. The assemblage appears potentially rich enough to support good growth of Fish at their larval stage when most fish depend on zooplankton as food. It was therefore concluded that the river has a potentially strong influence in the development of aquaculture, fisheries research and nutrition of the inhabitants of the State and its environs and can serve as a dependable resource pool for enhanced nutrition of the populace, fisheries development, teaching and research if the status is enhanced or at least maintained to conserve the fishery through adequate fisheries environmental management strategies.

KEYWORDS: Zooplankton, species, assemblage, abundance, biodiversity, Freshwater

INTRODUCTION

Zooplankton are microscopic invertebrate animals that swim or drift in water. They are at the base of the food chain. Fish prefer to eat the larger and more visible kinds of zooplankton, Therefore zooplankton that coexist with fish are typically small (less than 1 to 1.5 millimeters) and transparent (Anonymous, 2007). Zooplankton are heterotrophic planktonic animals floating in water which constitute an important foodsource for many species of aquatic organism (Guy, 1992). It consists of Protozoan, Cladocera, Copepoda, Rotifera, etc which may serve as indicators of water quality. Tucker (1992) reported zooplankton to be rich in the essential amino and fatty acids, Docosahexaenoic Acid (DHA) and Elcosaptaenoic acid (EPA). Zooplankton provide fish with nutrients since fish require proteins, fats, carbohydrates, mineral salts and water in the right proportion (Guy, 1992). Zooplankton study is of necessity in fisheries, aquaculture and limnological research. They are globally recognized as pollution indicator organisms in the aquatic environment (Yakubu *et al.*, 2000).

In Nigeria the study of zooplankton has been developed mostly in large rivers and lakes. Such studies have focused on descriptive ecology emphasising faunal composition, spatial and temporal distribution and plankton succession in newly-formed reservoirs (Green, 1960; Clark, 1978; Segers, 1993). Less attention has been given to smaller rivers which are scattered all over the country and contribute substantially to the nation's aquatic biodiversity.

Scientists are faced with the challenge to provide baseline studies on freshwater at regional and global scales, to international policy makers (Postel, 2001). Indeed monitoring the status and trends of freshwater biodiversity is essential to quantify impacts of human activities on freshwater systems and to improve freshwater biodiversity conservation. Estimating global trends for freshwater biodiversity will also be a critical asset for management strategies considering that studies on climate change and water resources and data management systems are currently being developed at a global scale (Leveque *et al.*, 2005).

FAO (2004) reported that not only have rivers been under-valued in conservation efforts but also ecological understanding of community and assemblage dynamics in low land rivers lags behind other fields of study (e.g. Limnology in temperate Lakes).

Echara River a freshwater river system which stems from lower Ebonyi River and confluence with Cross River. The river drains a large basin covering communities in Ebonyi State. Apart from its relevance as source of fish, portable water is sourced from the river by Ebonyi State Water Corporation. It is also used for irrigation and transportation. The riparian forest houses a rich wildlife. In spite of the multiple uses of the river, very little is known of its limnology. This study is therefore aimed at providing baseline information on the zooplankton of the river. Such information is vital in overall assessment of aquatic biodiversity in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area (Echara River) is located in the old Abakaliki zone, South-eastern Nigeria. The climate of the region is tropical. There are two distinct seasons within the zone. A rainy season (April to September) and the dry season (October to March). The river is fished all year round. The catchment area of the river is agricultural.

Samples for zooplankton analysis were collected monthly from four stations in the river between September 2006 and February 2008, with sampling bottles according to APHA, (1999) and filtered using plankton net of 45µm mesh size. The samples were pooled and preserved in 4% formalin. Quantitative analytical protocol was used to estimate the zooplankton under light microscope at 100x magnification using the sedge-wick rafter counting chamber. Five sub-samples of 1 ml each were usually counted from each collected sample and the mean density used to compute abundance. Taxonomic keys of Edmondson (1959), Pennak(1978), Koste (1978), Segers (1993), Segers, *et al.*, (1993), and Mergeay *et al.*, (2005) were used for identification. Abundance of zooplankton was estimated individual/ml of the original sample using the equation:

$$D = \frac{T (1000 \times Vc)}{AN \times Vs}$$

Where:

D = Density of plankton (individual /ml)

T = Total number of plankters counted

A = Area of grid in mm²

N = Number of grids employed

1000 = Area of counting chamber in mm²

Vc = Volume of concentration

Vs = Volume of sample

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the overall significance of the monthly means of the values recorded in locations. Fisher's Least Significant Difference (F-LSD) was used to separate the means and determine their interactions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Checklist of Zooplankton species assemblage of Echara River is presented in Table 1. Four groups (protozoans, rotifers, cladocerans and copepods) and 21 species were recorded. Cladocerans recorded the highest number of species (8), while Rotifers and Copepods each recorded 5 species. The least in terms of species Diversity is protozoans.

The result of the monthly mean values of zooplankton assemblage of Echara River is presented in Table 2. Each group differed significantly (P<0.01) from the other. There was non-significant interaction between rotifers, cladocerans and copepods. However, protozoan and nauplii showed significant (P<0.05) interactions. There was also significant difference (P<0.01) between the mean values of the groups in different locations. The mean monthly variation of zooplankton groups and inter-stational variation are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

The highest in abundance was copepods whose peak was in March 2007 (61 Org/L) followed by cladocerans which recorded 49 Orgs/L in April. The abundance of the remaining groups, Rotifers, protozoans and nauplii appear in descending order as shown in figure 1. In comparison, while rotifers of rivers Sokoto and Osun were dominated by *Brachionus furcatus* and *B. caudatus* (Egborge, 1974; Green, 1960), *Filina longiseta* and *Hexarthra mira* dominated the rotifer of Echara River.

The relative abundance of Zooplankton in relation to stations Fig 2 indicates location 2 as the highest in all the groups.

The trend in zooplankton abundance in Echara River indicated that it was more in abundance during the months of the dry season and less during the months of the wet season. This is in consonance with Mitsch and Gosselink (2000) who reported that the biodiversity of aquatic ecosystems depends upon and is determined primarily by their hydrological characteristics; and to a great extent by the nutrient status. Spatial and temporal variations in the amount of water and its source (precipitation, runoff or marine) generate the habitat heterogeneity and thereby affect the biodiversity (Keddy, 2000). High sediment loads in rivers and siltation of water bodies directly affect the biodiversity in various ways such as smothering of organisms, reduction in primary production and burial of seeds. (Keddy, 2000; Gopal and Chauhan, 2001).

Most of the identified species are cosmopolitan and have been previously seen in other Nigerian inland waters (Bedwell and Clarke, 1977; Onwudinjo and Egborge, 1994; Akinbuwa and Adeniyi, 1996; Akin-Oriola, 2003).

From the results generated, it can be concluded that the River is fairly rich in terms of zooplankton abundance and diversity. It is therefore clear that Echara River has a potentially strong influence in the development of fisheries since the zooplankton interaction of the river is healthy enough to support fish production. The river can serve as a dependable resource pool for fisheries development, teaching and research if the status is enhanced or at least maintained to conserve the resource through employing ecosystem approach to Fisheries governance.

REFERENCES

Akinbuwa, O. and Adeniyi, I. F. (1996). Seasonal variation, distribution and interrelationships of rotifers in Opa Reservoir, Nigeria. *Afr. J. Ecol.*, 34, 351-363.

American Public Health Association (APHA) 1999. Standard Method for the examination of water and waste waters. 18 edn, Washington DC. 1134pp.

Akin-Oriola, G.A. 2003. Zooplankton associations and environmental factors in Ogunpa and Ona Rivers Nigeria. *Revista de Biología Tropical.*, 51, 99-106.

Bedwell, A and Clarke, N.V. 1977. The invertebrate fauna of lake Kainji. *Nigeria Field.*, 42, 104-110.

Edmondson, W.T. (1959), Freshwater Biology. John Wiley and Sons Inc. New York 1248pp.

Egborge, A. 1974. Plankton of the River Oshun Nigeria. The seasonal variation and distribution of the zooplankton. *West Afric. Sci. Assoc.*, 19, 39- 53.

Gopal, B. and Chauhan, M. 2001. Biodiversity in Wetlands: Assessments, Functions and Conservation 2 edn, Backhuys Publishers, Leiden: 302pp.

Green J. 1960. Zooplankton of the River Sokoto. The rotifera. *In: Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London.*, 135, 491-523.

Guy, D. (1992). The ecology of the fish pond ecosystem with special reference to Africa. Pergamon Press 220 – 230pp.

Keddy, P.A. 2000. Wetland Ecology: Principles and Conservation, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge UK 614pp.

Koste, W. 1978. Rotatoria. Die Radetiere Mitteleuropas. Bestimmungswerk begründet von Max Voigt. 2 vols. Borntraeger, Stuttgart.

Leveque, C., Balian, E.V. and Martens, K. 2005. An assessment of animal species diversity in continental waters. *Hydrobiologia* 542:39-67.

Mergeay, J., Verschuren, D. and De Meester, L. 2005. Daphnia species diversity in Kenya, and a key to identification of their ephippia. *Hydrobiologia* 542:261-274.

Mitsch, W.J. and Gosselink, R. L. 2000. Wetlands. 3 edn. John Wiley, New York; 920pp.

Onwudinjjo, C.C and Egborge, A.B.M. 1994. Rotifers of Benin River, Nigeria. *Hydrobiologia.*, 272, 87-94.

Pennak, R. 1989. Freshwater invertebrates of the United States. 3rd edition. John Wiley and Sons, New York. 803pp.

Postel, S. 2001. Troubled waters. *Nature.* 87:58-105.

Segers, H. 1993. Rotifera of some lakes in the Floodplain of the River Niger. New species and other considerations. *Hydrobiologia* 250:39-61.

Segers, H., Nwandiario, S.C. and Dumont, H.J. 1993. Rotifera of some lakes in the floodplain of the River Niger (Imo State, Nigeria). *Hydrobiologia.*, 250, 63- 71.

Tucker, J. W. (1992). Feeding intensively cultured marine fish larvae p.129-146. In Allan G. I. & Dall, W. (eds). Proceedings of the Aquaculture Nutrition Workshop Salamander Bay, 15-17th April, 1991. NSW Fisheries, Brackish Water Fish Culture Research Station, Salamander Bay, Australia.

Yakubu, A. F., Sikoki, F. D., Abowei, J.F.N. and Hart, S. A. (2000). A comparative study of phytoplankton communities of some rivers creeks and borrow pits in the Niger Delta Area. *Journal of Applied Science, Environment and Management*, 4(2):41-46

TABLE 1: Checklist of Zooplankton Species Assemblage of Echara River

	MONTHS (2006 – 2008)																	
	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F
PROTOZOANS																		
<i>Codorella crata</i>	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Diffugia lobostoma</i>	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
<i>Veiticella sp.</i>	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
ROTIFERS																		
<i>Brachyonus calyciflonus</i>	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+
<i>Filina longiseta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Hexarthra mira</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+
<i>Polyarthra vulgaris</i>	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
<i>Keratella coculearis</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
CLADOCERANS																		
<i>Bosminopsis deitersi</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Latonopsis occidentalis</i>	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Pleuroxus denticulatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Diaphanosoma birgei</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Acroperus harpae</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>Moina micrura</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Moina brachiata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Kurzia latissima</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
COPEPODS																		
<i>Orthocyclops modestus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Episcura Lacustris</i>	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Ergasilus chautauquensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Diacyclopsbicipidatus thomasi</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Scapholeberis armata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

KEY: + = Present, - = Absent

Table 2: Summary of Means and Interaction of zooplankton collage in Echara River

Months(M)	Rotifers	Cladocerans	Copepods	Protozoan	Nauplii
September 2006	2.750	24.000	13.750	0.125	0.000
October 2006	2.500	23.250	15.380	0.000	0.000
November 2006	2.375	22.880	17.250	0.125	0.125
December 2006	2.375	25.380	19.120	0.750	0.750
January 2007	2.625	26.880	20.000	0.375	0.375
February 2007	4.500	35.120	25.120	1.000	1.000
March 2007	5.500	47.000	61.500	1.000	1.000
April 2007	3.750	49.250	50.380	0.625	0.625
May 2007	1.375	22.000	7.250	0.000	0.000
June 2007	0.875	19.500	4.500	0.000	0.250
July 2007	0.625	13.620	2.370	0.250	0.000
August 2007	1.000	4.000	4.750	0.000	0.000
September 2007	0.000	5.620	4.000	0.000	0.000
October 2007	1.375	22.25	9.380	0.375	0.250
November 2007	2.125	20.62	17.620	0.375	0.375
December 2007	0.875	21.75	20.120	0.375	0.375
January 2008	2.250	27.120	20.500	0.500	0.500
February 2008	3.125	33.000	24.000	1.000	1.125
FLSD _(0.05)	0.8552**	4.805**	4.221**	0.5572**	0.5120**
LOCATIONS(L)					
1	2.194	25.640	18.530	0.250	0.250
2	2.917	27.920	22.000	1.000	0.944
3	1.972	22.920	17.250	0.111	0.139
4	1.806	22.030	17.110	0.167	0.167
FLSD _(0.05)	0.4031**	2.265**	1.990**	0.5572	0.2414**
Interactions(M x L)	NS	NS	NS	1.1144*	1.0240*

Levels of significance: * = p<0.05; ** =p<0.01 and NS = Not significant

Figure 1: Relative Monthly Abundance of Zooplankton in Echara River

Figure 2: Relative Locations Abundance of Zooplanktons in Echara River

Received for Publication: 11/03/2011

Accepted for Publication: 02/04/2011

Corresponding author

Ude, E. F.,

Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Ebonyi State University, P. M. B. 053, Abakaliki, Nigeria.

E-mail: emm_ude@yahoo.co.uk